

UNDERSTANDING EDUCATION THROUGH THE DIALECTIC METHOD

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Abstract

In this study, it was assumed that the pedagogical process is marked by a dialectic that is not always perceptible to the teacher, who often interprets learning as disconnected from the whole, as an accumulation of information. In addition, most of the teachers disregard that in this process there are advances and retreats and that it is based on a socio-historical context. It is proposed in this dissertation to cover categories that facilitate such understanding, which may resize these practices in the sense of consciously building a dialectical pedagogy. For this reason, it is understood as essential to rescue language and the principles of dialectics and mediation, conceived from a socio-historical-dialectical point of view.

Keywords: Education; Pedagogy; Dialectic; Philosophical foundations.

About the author

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INTRODUCTION

A concern among Brazilian scholars and researchers has been the superficial dissemination of the theories of Bakhtin, Vygotsky and Luria and the creation of a kind of fad. This is a relevant concern, since the history of Brazilian education has shown changes in theories that support the debate on the educational process without, however, having been contextualized apprehension of them or how these theories interfere or could interfere in the school routine. It is possible to perceive with this a certain diversity on the part of the teachers, that is, there is not the proper understanding and differentiation of one from the other. Studies on the philosophical foundations of education help the reader to develop their own criticisms and perceive the interference of these theories in school work, especially in written production. They allow, in this way, a better clarification of the theories that are present in the school routine and, consequently, a better understanding of the advances that the socio-historical theory, when effectively apprehended by the teacher, can make possible.

When considering the theoretical diversity that underlies the work of a large number of professors, it was perceived the need to situate the development of the socio-historical approach in Brazil, focusing on some contributions that the theories developed by

Vygotsky, Luria and Bakhtin have given us. offered to rethink the educational process. The discussion about the Marxist dialectical conception in the approach of the authors and the principle of mediation, from which language is also discussed, was considered fundamental here.

HISTORICAL CONTEXT

The works of Vygotsky, Luria and Bakhtin began to be discussed in Brazil from the mid-1970s onwards. To better understand the context of that time, it is necessary to go back a little further in time. In the 1960s, the popular culture movement was concerned with the participation of the people in the political and cultural process. In this movement, young people guided by a Christian and leftist thought were engaged, the latter having the influence of a Marxist-Leninist perspective. During this period, based on Freire's theories, many educators tried to place education at the service of the popular classes, having, among other goals, the process of popular awareness, to place the working class in the face of national problems and engage them in the political struggle.

According to Lira (2010), this movement, however, was repressed by the 1964 coup, from which the concern for an education aimed at training a more qualified workforce was officially accentuated, as required by commerce

and industry. Thus, priority was given to a pedagogy inserted in the rationalist model, which stood out for its technical and methodological aspects. Simultaneously with this technicist trend, in the 60s and 70s Piaget's writings gained prominence. From this author's perspective, the child's development was valued from an individual point of view. It can be noted, therefore, that the Piagetian theory at that time represented an advance in relation to the conception of the child as an active being, capable of interfering in the school learning process. However, the same theory also had points compatible with technicism, insofar as both were based on a liberal ideology that defended the technical-neutral aspect of education.

In the seventies, studies on the characteristics of poor children oscillated between the deficit thesis and the difference thesis, with one often being confused with the other. Patto (2022) states that the "difference theory" became subjugated by the "deficit theory" because, according to the author, the difference thesis subtly contained the disability thesis. Both one and the other considered the school as capable of overcoming social marginality, being endowed with autonomy to solve the cultural problems that occurred in it. None, however, questioned the socioeconomic causes of school failure. They ignored the essential causes for the problems they wanted

to solve and did not propose to recognize and identify the real role of the school in the social structure.

The concept of cultural deficiency to justify school failure was explained by the living conditions of the ruling class, which allow a wealth of experiences - habits, attitudes, knowledge, skills, interests - enabling children from this class to have relative success in school. Patto says:

It is important to note that if in the years when the theory of cultural deficiency prevailed, intra-school aspects received little attention, and if during the validity of the theory of cultural difference, the school's responsibility for failure was limited to its inadequacy for the clientele, as research goes on revealing more critically aspects of the structure and functioning of the school system, instead of overcoming the tendency to attribute to the clientele the causes of school failure, it was only added to considerations about the poor quality of education offered to these children (p. 213, 2022).

Through research, it was verified that the physical, intellectual, sensory, motor, emotional characteristics - the "environmental poverty" of lower class children, in short - would produce "deficiency" in the child's psychological development, becoming the cause of their difficulties school. Consequently, the social structure was not criticized as responsible for school failure, but the student, for having cultural deficits.

At the end of the 1970s and beginning of the following decade, studies regarding the link between society and school were guided by the reading of the French authors Bourdieu and Passeron. These authors analyzed the reproductive aspect of production relations and the cultural and ideological domination present in social institutions. With regard to the school, they denounced the appreciation of the style of thought, language and attitudes characteristic of the dominant class, in addition to content that ideologically would be at the service of the reproduction of production relations and maintenance of the “status quo”. Despite the considerable advances provided by the apprehension of the theory of these authors by Brazilian educators.

Several researchers, supporters of the theory of cultural deprivation, thus began to cite the theory of reproduction, taking it in an uncritical way, mixing one with the other. But, despite some misreadings, Bourdieu and Passeron's thesis played, in the mid-1970s, an important role in changing Brazilian educational thinking. It served, for example, to highlight the relational dimension of the teaching-learning process, opening space for the perception of the importance of the teacher-student relationship, even when technicalities, in force, relegated the psychosocial dimension of pedagogical relationships to the background. This thesis drew attention to the existing social

domination and discrimination in teaching and offered possibilities for school education to be thought of from its social constraints. It therefore contributed, together with other Marxist references, to the perception of the myth of the neutrality of the educational process, opening the way for further understanding of reproductive ideas and for the incorporation of theories that would enable the insertion of reflections on school in a dialectical conception of totality.

At the end of the military regime, in the 1980s, political mobilizations intensified; the people taking to the streets demanding “direct now” created a political revival that extended to the educational area. Groups organized themselves with the aim of rethinking the school, actively participating in organizations such as the Brazilian Society for the Progress of Science (SBPC), the National Association of Graduate Studies in Education (Anped) and the National Commission for the Reformulation of Training Courses of Educators (CONARCFE), current National Association for the Training of Education Professionals (ANFOPE), among others. In addition to these organizations, the Brazilian Education Conferences (CBEs) became important forums for debates in which the role of educators in society was rethought. Theories that supported productions in the educational field (such as critical-reproductivist ones), Traditional Pedagogy and the various

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aspects of New Pedagogy were the target of criticism, which opened up space for a pedagogical thought guided by a democratic and socialist conception of the world. In this context, the theories of Vygotsky, Luria and Bakhtin were taken as references for a new perspective of Education.

FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES OF EDUCATIONAL PRAXIS

Vygotsky, Luria and Bakhtin were contemporaries in the post-revolutionary Soviet Union. The historical and dialectical materialism of Karl H. Marx (1818-1883) and Friedrich Engels (1820-1895) represented an important subsidy for their own theoretical elaborations, and based on the referred materialism they tried to understand the man in his totality, perceiving the reality as a product of human actions in the world and their influence on man himself. In this sense, categories worked on by Marx and Engels such as mediation, contradiction, historicity and totality pervade the theories developed by Soviet authors.

According to the Marxist conception, man, in the social process of production and reproduction, creates the infrastructure and the superstructure that form social reality as a totality of social relations, institutions and ideas. In this process, he creates himself as a

historical and social being, carrying out the infinite project of “humanization of man”. To understand this reality, man needs to leave the immediate perception of the object of knowledge to a mediate dimension, seeking to reveal the relationships that are enclosed in the object under study,

For Carvalho and Pio, (2017) praxis, that is, reflected action, is also the criterion that enables the perception of contradictions inserted in the object and thought. Thus, in order to reflect in a non-contradictory way, it is necessary to discover contradictions in thought, which will contribute to its development, regardless of the nature of these contradictions. As for the totality, this does not mean capturing and scrutinizing all its aspects, since the isolated facts become artificial, in the same way the perception of the whole without the apprehension of the parts becomes empty and abstract. Thus, for Torres (1979) to understand the dialectic of totality, it is necessary to realize that the parts are interrelated and connected with each other and with the whole, and this, in turn, is not watertight, as it is created in the interaction with the parts. This is how, for example, Bakhtin analyzed language: he sought to perceive it in its entirety, not just analyzing it in its graphic and phonic aspects, as in this way it would become artificial. Likewise, to apprehend the meaning of the enunciation, it is necessary to understand the elements that

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compose it so that it does not become empty of meaning. The Russian linguist Bakhtin analyzed the meaning of the words that make up the enunciation, in its ideological aspect, inserted in a real context of significant exchanges, in which the meanings of the word vary according to the circumstance in which it is produced. He thus highlighted the “living” language that is constantly changing.

According to Sanches Vasquez (2007), Bakhtin, opposing current thinking - which conceived language as an abstract and closed system - defended the need to place it in the sphere of social relations, linked to speech, to become a fact of language. He realized that it is precisely in the flow of verbal communication, in enunciation, in the social-individual interrelationship, that language is processed and modified. He proposed a new way of treating language, inserting it in the social world, with its contradictions and ideologies.

In the educational field, reading the work of these authors offers valuable contributions and opens the way for a deeper understanding of the production of knowledge, which takes place in an interactive space, in a subject-subject-object-subject relationship. That is, in the relationship with the other, the subject establishes a relationship with the object of knowledge and in the relationship with the object of knowledge, he re-dimensions his

relationship with the other and re-dimensions himself.

Meeting points can be seen between the principles formulated by Marx on dialectics and those constructed by Vygotsky and Luria, when the latter assume that consciousness originates in practical activity and is built by the interaction of the subject with the object. Vygotsky also incorporated the Marxist understanding that the object under study must be analyzed as a moving and changing process and, in this sense, the Soviet author analyzed the transformation of elementary psychological processes into superior processes, taking as a goal the reconstruction of the origin and course of the development of consciousness.

The foundations of Marxist dialectics are also noted in Vygotsky and Luria, when they defend, as one of the basic postulates of socio-historical theory, the understanding that human psychological functions, unlike the psychological processes of other animals, are culturally mediated, develop historically and arise from practical activity. Based on this assumption, formal instruction is considered as a context of activities, in which human beings develop in determined historical and cultural circumstances. Thus, cultural mediation is fundamental, constituting the basis for anthropological elaborations that human beings live in an environment transformed by

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instruments. The main function of these instruments would be to adjust men with the physical world and with each other.

For Vygotsky, a complete theory of human development must encompass four historical levels simultaneously: the development of the species (phylogeny), the history of human beings as a differentiated species, the individual history of the human being (ontogeny) and the study of particular psychological processes, in experimental interactions in a single experimental session (microgeny). According to Becker (2003), the author thus sought to trace three basic lines of behavior development - evolutionary, historical and ontogenetic - to show the need for behavior to be scientifically understood and explained with the help of these three lines.

Becker (2003) also states that the dynamic way in which these three lines are inter defined constituted the originality of Vygotsky's approach. The reliance on genetic (evolutionary) analysis, the defense that the higher mental functions of the individual have their origins in social life (ontogenetics), and the idea according to which the key to understanding human psychological and social processes are the tools and instruments signs used for its mediation characterize the socio-cultural focus sustained by Vygotsky. Mediation is considered by Wertsch as superior to the other two lines of research, evolutionary and ontogenetic,

because, according to Vygotsky's own argument, mediation can be understood by itself, while the other two, in several aspects, need mediation to be understood.

It is clear, however, in Vygotsky's arguments, the importance of using these three lines of analysis so that the object can be perceived in a totalizing way, given that the analysis of mediations, without a historical understanding of the process, becomes it would be mechanical and superficial. In the first theme, Vygotsky insists on the use of genetic analysis to examine the functioning of the human mind, because through this form of analysis it is possible to specify its origins and the genetic transformations that man has experienced. Vygotsky's main concern in genetic analysis, which was originally continued by Luria, turned to evolutionary processes and also examined the effects of interruptions and interventions on them; for this reason he was concerned about deafness, blindness and mental retardation.

Vygotsky distinguished ontogeny from other fields of analysis, as this implies the simultaneous and interrelated analysis of several developmental forces. It allows a perception of development in its entirety, but it also prevents the isolated study of any of these forces. The same does not occur with phylogenesis, which makes it possible to study

certain explanatory principles with those of other genetic domains.

Darsie (1999) states that Luria, a collaborator of Vygotsky, also sharing the Marxist assumptions, defended that a scientific psychology should have as its object of research the social and historical origin of the superior forms of conscious activity, and should deal with the analysis of the complex forms of representation of reality, which are realized by the human brain and formed throughout humanity. Luria realized the great importance that historical and social conditions have in the creation of new and complex relationships with reality. His defense of the need to take into account the social conditions that shape man's psychic activity in detail, in order to obtain a solid scientific basis.

For Luria (1979), therefore, the main forms of man's psychic activity are born in the conditions of social history; the development of this activity takes place in the process of material activity that arises throughout history, based on the means formed in the work process, in the use of work instruments and language. According to the author, as well as for Marx, without the tools of work and language, man would be on the margins of the conditions of the material world, since he would be deprived of communication with the environment. In this way, he understands that man's activities are carried out by the brain, supported by the laws

of his superior processes, but this nervous system is incapable of ensuring the formation of the ability to use work tools and language, as well as explaining the emergence of complex forms of human activity developed in the process of social history.

According to Luria (1979), Vygotsky, when proposing the challenge of elaborating the theoretical bases of a Marxist psychology, "unlike the others, proposed that it was not the role of psychologists to formulate collections of quotes from Marx and Engels on the various aspects of human psychology, but to introduce the Marxist method into psychological science.

Vygotsky used as a base element for the development of his method Engels' assertion that not only does nature act on man, but man also acts on nature and reshapes it, according to his needs. Based on this thought, he developed his studies and interpretations of higher psychological functions. Along with the new research method, he saw the need to develop new analytical frameworks. In this regard, he developed three basic principles in the analysis of higher psychological functions.

The first of them was guided by the analysis of the process as opposed to the analysis of the object and to develop a process analysis it became necessary to develop a method that artificially provoked or created a process of psychological development. This method could be called the "development-experimental"

method. The second principle aimed at an analysis that revealed the causal relationships, which was explanatory and not descriptive. This principle was related to the third principle, which refers to the problem of “fossilized behavior”, in which he stated the need for the researcher to concentrate, not on the product of development, but on the process of establishing higher forms. For this, the researcher is often forced, through problem situations, to change the automatic, mechanized and fossilized character of higher forms of behavior, in an attempt to understand the process that generated such behavior.

In all these principles, Vygotsky's concern to develop a dialectical method of research that could encompass the object historically, researching it in all its phases and changes can be seen. According to that author, this form of apprehension of the object would be the main requirement that the dialectical method requires.

The works of Vygotsky, Luria and Bakhtin are, therefore, amalgamated in the principles of Marxist dialectics, organizing and dimensioning the way they conceive and reflect on the world, influencing the construction of a new research methodology. Discussions about language, about the role of interactions between peers, between the child and the adult, present both in Bakhtin's theoretical formulations and in other Soviet authors, have influenced

teaching and enabled the understanding of child development in a broader scope regarding its complexity.

In the sociocultural theory, elaborated by Vygotsky and his companions, some basic theses were developed: the first presents the biological basis of psychological functioning. The brain is seen as the main organ of mental activity, whose structure and functioning are developed throughout phylogenesis and ontogenesis. It is the material substratum of psychic activity that each member of the species brings with him at birth.

The second thesis presents the individual-society relationship. Vygotsky states that human characteristics are not innate, but the result of the dialectical interaction of man and his sociocultural environment. When man transforms his environment, he transforms himself as well. Thus, culture is a constitutive part of human nature, as it is through the internalization of historically constructed and culturally organized modes that its psychological characterization takes place.

The third thesis brings the idea that higher psychological processes cannot be reduced to a chain of reflexes, as these can only be explained and described taking into account the historical process in which they develop. Thus, when approaching human consciousness as a social product, it is necessary to study the

changes that occur in mental development from the social context.

The understanding that Bakhtin developed about language, as a concrete system, built in the dialogical process, also pointed to its importance in the formation and development of consciousness, being integrated into the historical and social existence of men. Thus, the word, which is constitutive of man as a subject and serves as a means of communication, permeates the system of relationships in which he is immersed. The word, “on the one hand, is linked to production processes and, on the other hand, concerns the spheres of the various specialized and formalized ideologies”. In this way, it promotes and suffers modifications according to the infrastructure and superstructure, indicating, in a sensitive way, all social transformations.

Vygotsky, Luria and Bakhtin re-dimensioned Marxist theory in the midst of their research, in contrast to the idealist subjectivism and abstract objectivism that prevailed in each field of study. Bakhtin, focusing mainly on language, criticized the theories that supported it and proposed a new way of treating it and that would be able to integrate it into the social world with its contradictions and ideologies. Vygotsky and Luria sought to develop their psychological research with the aim of proposing a dialectical psychology, capable of apprehending the

process of psychic development considering the construction of mediated behavior.

For Vygotsky, Luria and Bakhtin, instruments and signs are historically constructed and enable men to mediate among themselves and with the world. The sign is, therefore, a mediating element and, as such, interposes itself between man and the objects of his work, expanding the possibilities of transforming nature. Signs, being elements that represent or express other objects, events and situations, serve as “auxiliary means to solve a given psychological problem (remembering, comparing things, reporting, choosing, etc.), is analogous to the invention and use of the instrument, only that now in the psychological field. Mediation, as can be seen, constitutes a basic principle in the theses developed by the Soviets, from which it is conceived that the relationship between man and the environment is not always direct, but mediated by “auxiliary tools” of human activity.

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